

Fouling fan worms (Annelida, Sabellidae) from northern and central Mexican Pacific marinas and ports

Gusanos plumero incrustantes (Annelida: Sabellidae) de puertos y marinas del norte y centro del Pacífico mexicano

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ABSTRACT

Seven species of fouling sabellid worms are here reported attached to artificial submerged structures (fixed and floating docks, ropes, buoys, rafts, pilings, pneumatic tires and hull of vessels) from 68 localities in marinas and ports from Baja California, Baja California Sur, Colima, Jalisco, Nayarit and Sinaloa (western Mexico). *Acromegalomma coloratum* (Chamberlin, 1919), *Notaulax californica* (Treadwell, 1906), *Parasabella pallida* Moore, 1923, and *Pseudobranchiomma schizogenica* Tovar-Hernández & Dean, 2014 are reported for many new localities. *Parasabella rugosa* (Moore, 1904), described from San Diego, constitutes a new record for Mexico. *Paradialychone ecaudata* (Moore, 1923) is first recorded as biofouler, and *Pseudopotamilla* sp. is probably a new species.

Key words: Feather duster worms, harbor biota, northwestern Mexico, Sabellida, sclerobionts

RESUMEN

Se reportan siete especies de gusanos sabélidos adheridos a estructuras artificiales sumergidas (muelles fijos y flotantes, cabos sumergidos, boyas, balsas, pilotes, neumáticos y cascos de embarcaciones) de 68 localidades en marinas y puertos de Baja California, Baja California Sur, Colima, Jalisco, Nayarit y Sinaloa (México noroccidental). *Acromegalomma coloratum* (Chamberlin, 1919), *Notaulax californica* (Treadwell, 1906), *Parasabella pallida* Moore, 1923, y *Pseudobranchiomma schizogenica* Tovar-Hernández & Dean, 2014 son registradas en nuevas localidades. *Parasabella rugosa* (Moore, 1904),

descrita de San Diego, constituye un nuevo registro para México. *Paradialychone ecaudata* (Moore, 1923) se registra por primera vez como incrustante de estructuras antropogénicas. *Pseudopotamilla* sp. es probablemente una nueva especie.

Palabras clave: Biota portuaria, esclerobiontes, gusanos plumero, México noroccidental, Sabellida

INTRODUCTION

Sabellidae members are among the most easily recognizable annelid groups due to their possession of an often colorful branchial crown and by the mucus/parchment of sediment tubes that they generally inhabit (Capa et al. 2021, Rouse et al. 2022). The family comprises over 512 nominal species described to date, currently grouped in 42 genera (Capa et al. 2021). Besides, sabellids constitute one of the most important taxa in the marine fouling biota (Tovar-Hernández et al. 2009b, Keppel et al. 2015, Kupriyanova et al. 2016). Some species, such as *Sabella spallanzanii* (Gmelin, 1791) and *Branchiomma bairdi* (McIntosh, 1885), are targeted as marine pests (Capa et al. 2021).

The study of fouling worms in Mexico begun 16 years ago, particularly focused in tubicolous worms from the port of Mazatlán, Mexican Pacific (Tovar-Hernández et al. 2009a-b). Posteriorly, studies were expanded along the Gulf of California, Central and Southern Mexican Pacific, including errant and sedentariate worms, and a variety of subjects on faunistic, establishment of new species, reproduction, ecology, distribution and genetics (Tovar-Hernández et al. 2011, 2012, 2014, 2016, 2019, 2020, 2022, 2024; Villalobos-Guerrero & Tovar-Hernández, 2013, 2014; Tovar-Hernández & Yáñez-Rivera, 2009a, 2009b; Tovar-Hernández & Dean, 2014; Bastida-Zavala et al. 2016; Galván-Villa et al. 2023; Kupriyanova et al. 2024; Palma-Neri & Bastida-Zavala 2024; Ramos-Morales et al. 2024). In addition, polychaete fouling samples from Mexico have been used to clarify the distribution of species in Australia (Sun et al. 2016), United States of America (Keppel et al. 2015, 2018), and the Mediterranean Sea (del Pasqua et al. 2018).

The present study is part of a broad project entitled “Evaluación de poliquetos exóticos invasores en marinas y puertos de México”, supported by the Fondo Sectorial de Investigación Ambiental (grant SEMARNAT-CONACYT A3-S-73811). Exhaustive sampling was conducted in the first semester of 2021 by 33 colleagues in 10 states of Mexico, 24 marinas and ports, and six natural protected areas, summarizing more than 100 sampling sites. This contribution presents the composition of seven fouling members of Sabellidae from Western Mexico, whereas records of large colonies of *Pseudopotamilla socialis* Hartman, 1944 are being recorded by Tovar-Hernández et al. (2025, under revision), and the study of four species of *Branchiomma* Kölliker, 1858 is in process including *B. bairdi* (McIntosh, 1885), *B. cingulatum* (Grube, 1870), *B. coheni* Tovar-Hernández & Knight-Jones, 2006, *B. conspersum* (Ehlers, 1887) and several other genetic lineages involved.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Sampling was carried out in anthropogenic substrates from marinas, ports, and natural protected areas from Mexico, in 2021, under the permission granted by the Comisión Nacional de Acuacultura y Pesca (DGOPA.14011.151012.3291). Sampling, relaxation and fixation follow the standardized protocol by Pech et al. (2023). The data of stations here reported are presented in Table 1.

The morphological examination was performed using a Leica MZ75 stereomicroscope and an Olympus CH30 high-power microscope. Photographs were taken with an attached Canon EOS Rebel T7i digital camera. Shirlastain A was helpful in analysis of the main morphological features as well as Methyl green to reveal glandular shields. Identification was based on specialized literature, as indicated in the systematics section of each species. Descriptions are not included since the morphology of the species herein reported has been addressed in previous contributions. The nomenclature and taxonomic remarks sections also include references of systematic contributions for further details. Formulae describing frequency of unpaired compound eyes in different radioles on the right side of the crown in *Pseudopotamilla* Bush, 1905 follow Knight-Jones et al. (2017).

Biodiversity information is referred to the geographic ecoregions and provinces proposed by Spalding et al.

(2007). All sabellid specimens studied here were deposited in the Colección Poliquetológica de la Universidad Autónoma de Nuevo León (UANL, NL-INV-0002-05-09), Mexico.

Table 1. Sampling stations, all from superficial water, not deeper than 1 m. ND: not determined.

ID	LOCALITY	SITE	LATITUDE N	LONGITUDE W	SUBSTRATE	COLLECTORS	S (ppt)	T (°C)	pH	O2 (mg/l)
BLA-S-20210511-1	Bahía de los Ángeles	Bahía de los Angeles	28°56'49.68"	113°32'57.18"	Buoy (plastic)	MMR, OMG & VDC	35,5	21,2	8	11,1
BLA-S-20210511-2	Bahía de los Ángeles	Bahía de los Angeles	28°56'49.68"	113°32'57.18"	Buoy (plastic)	MMR, OMG & VDC	35,5	21,2	8	11,1
CLP-A-Q-20210313-2	La Paz	Marina Cantamar La Paz	24°16'44"	110°19'52"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	JALG, MEGG, GGG & CCT	ND	ND	N D	ND
ENS-A-Q-20210315-1	Puerto de Ensenada	API, Muelle	31°51'31.92"	116°37'32.64"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	FFS & MRO	33,9	15,4	8	4,7
ENS-A-Q-20210315-2	Puerto de Ensenada	API, Muelle	31°51'31.92"	116°37'32.64"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	FFS & MRO	33,9	15,4	8	7,7
ENS-A-Q-20210315-6	Puerto de Ensenada	API, Muelle	31°51'22.08"	116°37'44.58"	Hull ship (metal)	FFS & MRO	33,6	14,9	8	4,1
ENS-A-Q-20210315-7	Puerto de Ensenada	API, Muelle	31°51'24.84"	116°37'51.90"	Fixed dock (concrete)	FFS & MRO	33,8	15,4	8	5
ENS-B-Q-20210315-4	Puerto de Ensenada	API, Boya	31°49'34.14"	116°37'35.88"	Buoy (plastic)	FFS & MRO	33,8	14,9	8	7,3
ENS-B-Q-20210315-6	Puerto de Ensenada	API, Boya	31°49'34.14"	116°37'35.88"	Buoy (plastic)	FFS & MRO	33,8	14,9	8	7,3
ENS-B-Q-20210315-7	Puerto de Ensenada	API, Boya	31°50'54.42"	116°37'10.20"	Buoy (metal)	FFS & MRO	33,8	15,1	8	5,4
ENS-B-Q-20210315-9	Puerto de Ensenada	API, Boya	31°50'54.42"	116°37'10.20"	Buoy (metal)	FFS & MRO	33,8	15,1	8	5,4
ENS-S-20210315-1	Puerto de Ensenada	API, Muelle	31°51'0.48"	116°37'41.16"	Fixed dock (concrete)	FFS & MRO	33,8	15	8	5,1
ENS-S-20210315-2	Puerto de Ensenada	API, Muelle	31°51'24.84"	116°37'51.90"	Hull ship (metal)	FFS & MRO	33,8	15,4	8	5

Sabellid polychaetes from marinas and ports of Mexico

Table 1 continued

FLP-S-2-20210312	La Paz	Marina FONATUR La Paz	24°07'30"	110°20'47"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	JALG, MEGG, GGG & CCT	ND	20	ND	ND
MAN-A-Q-20210429-2	Puerto de Manzanillo	Muelle de pescadores	19°03'14.3"	104°18'38.4"	Fixed dock (concrete)	CGV	35,2	20,9	ND	5,08
MAN-A-Q-20210429-7	Puerto de Manzanillo	Muelle de pescadores	19°03'15.5"	104°18'39.0"	Fixed dock (concrete)	CGV	35,2	20,8	ND	4,54
MAN-A-Q-20210429-9	Puerto de Manzanillo	Muelle de pescadores	19°03'15.5"	104°18'39.0"	Fixed dock (concrete)	CGV	35,2	20,7	ND	4,16
MANA-S-20210508-1	Marismas Nacionales	Boca del Camichín	21°44'41.838"	105°29'48.222"	Sclerozoan of oyster <i>Crassostrea corteziensis</i> attached to dock	MATH	ND	ND	ND	ND
MANA-S-20210521	Marismas Nacionales	Boca del Camichín	21°44'18.3"	105°29'31.0"	Rustic raft of plastic containers	RA, FR & PSS	30	30,4	ND	ND
MZT-A-Q-20210324-1	Mazatlán	Marina Mazatlán	23°16'17"	106°27'18"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	FVM	36	21	ND	ND
MZT-A-Q-20210324-2	Mazatlán	Marina Mazatlán	23°16'17"	106°27'18"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	FVM	36	21	ND	ND
MZT-A-Q-20210324-4	Mazatlán	Marina Mazatlán	23°16'10"	106°27'16"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	FVM	36	22,5	ND	ND
MZT-A-Q-20210324-5	Mazatlán	Marina Mazatlán	23°16'10"	106°27'16"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	FVM	36	22,5	ND	ND
MZT-A-Q-20210324-6	Mazatlán	Marina Mazatlán	23°16'10"	106°27'16"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	FVM	36	22,5	ND	ND
MZT-A-Q-20210324-7	Mazatlán	Marina Mazatlán	23°16'14"	106°27'19"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	FVM	36	22,5	ND	ND
MZT-B-Q-20210319-1	Puerto de Mazatlán	API, canal de navegación	23°10'56"	106°25'7"	Buoy (metal)	FVM	36	17,2	ND	ND

Table 1 continued

MZT-B-Q-20210319-2	Puerto de Mazatlán	API, canal de navegación	23°10'56"	106°25'7"	Buoy (metal)	FVM	36	17, 2	ND	ND
MZT-B-Q-20210319-7	Puerto de Mazatlán	API, canal de navegación	23°12'32"	108°24'7"	Buoy (metal)	FVM	37	18	ND	ND
MZT-B-Q-20210319-8	Puerto de Mazatlán	API, canal de navegación	23°12'32"	108°24'7"	Buoy (metal)	FVM	37	18	ND	ND
MZT-S-20210315-1	Puerto de Mazatlán	API, canal de navegación	23°10'55.76"	106°25'28.01"	Rope	SHT	37	18	ND	ND
MZT-S-20210324-1	Puerto de Mazatlán	Marina Mazatlán	23°16'14"	106°27'19"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	MATH	36	23, 5	ND	ND
NAY-A-Q-20210315-1	La Cruz de Huanacastle	Marina Riviera Nayarit	20°45'00.8"	105°22'42.7"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	FR, CCG & RA	35	23, 3	7	ND
NAY-A-Q-20210315-2	La Cruz de Huanacastle	Marina Riviera Nayarit	20°45'00.8"	105°22'42.7"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	FR, CCG & RA	35	23, 3	7	ND
NAY-A-Q-20210316-4	La Cruz de Huanacastle	Marina Riviera Nayarit	20°44'57.6"	105°22'50.3"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	FR, CCG & RA	37	23, 5	7	ND
NAY-A-Q-20210316-6	La Cruz de Huanacastle	Marina Riviera Nayarit	20°44'57.7"	105°22'49.7"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	FR, CCG & RA	38	24, 7	7	ND
NAY-A-Q-20210317-7	La Cruz de Huanacastle	Marina Riviera Nayarit	20°44'54.2"	105°22'48.3"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	FR, CCG & RA	35	22, 7	7	ND
NAY-A-Q-20210317-8	La Cruz de Huanacastle	Marina Riviera Nayarit	20°44'53.0"	105°22'49.3"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	FR, CCG & RA	35	22, 7	7	ND
NAY-A-Q-20210317-9	La Cruz de Huanacastle	Marina Riviera Nayarit	20°44'53.0"	105°22'50.1"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	FR, CCG & RA	35	22, 2	7	ND
PVA-B-Q-20210419-1	Puerto Vallarta	Entrada a la Dársena	20°39'13"	105°14' 41.90"	Buoy (metal)	PSS, FR, RA & CCG	37	25, 6	5	ND

Sabellid polychaetes from marinas and ports of Mexico

Table 1 continued

PVA-B-Q-20210419-4	Puerto Vallarta	Entrada a la Dársena	20°39'15.5"	105°14'40.5"	Buoy (metal)	PSS, FR, RA & CCG	37	25,7	5	ND
PVA-B-Q-20210419-5	Puerto Vallarta	Entrada a la Dársena	20°39'15.5"	105°14'40.5"	Buoy (metal)	PSS, FR, RA & CCG	37	25,7	5	ND
PVA-B-Q-20210419-6	Puerto Vallarta	Entrada a la Dársena	20°39'15.5"	105°14'40.5"	Buoy (metal)	PSS, FR, RA & CCG	37	25,7	5	ND
PVA-B-Q-20210419-7	Puerto Vallarta	Entrada a la Dársena	20°39'24.1"	105°14'44.8"	Buoy (metal)	PSS, FR, RA & CCG	37	28,3	5	ND
PVA-B-Q-20210419-9	Puerto Vallarta	Entrada a la Dársena	20°39'24.1"	105°14'44.8"	Buoy (metal)	PSS, FR, RA & CCG	37	28,3	5	ND
PVA-S-20210325-2	Puerto Vallarta	Playa los muertos	20°44'53.0"	105°22'50.1"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	PSS & FR	35	22,5	6	ND
SAR-A-Q-20210309-1	Santa Rosalía	Marina FONATUR Santa Rosalía	27°20'14"	112°15'48"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	JALG, MEGG, GGG & CCT	N/D	20,5	ND	ND
SAU-A-Q-20210326-1	Puerto de El Sauzal	API, Muelle	31°53'33.48"	116°42'14.10"	Fixed dock (concrete)	ERG	33,7	14,6	8	3,5
SAU-A-Q-20210326-2	Puerto de El Sauzal	API, Muelle	31°53'33.48"	116°42'14.10"	Fixed dock (concrete)	ERG	33,7	14,6	8	3,5
SAU-A-Q-20210326-3	Puerto de El Sauzal	API, Muelle	31°53'33.48"	116°42'14.10"	Fixed dock (concrete)	ERG	33,7	14,6	8	3,5
SAU-A-Q-20210326-4	Puerto de El Sauzal	API, Muelle	31°53'39.66"	116°42'8.34"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	ERG	33,6	15,1	8	2,7
SAU-A-Q-20210326-5	Puerto de El Sauzal	API, Muelle	31°53'39.66"	116°42'8.34"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	ERG	33,6	15,1	8	2,7
SAU-B-Q-20210326-1	Puerto de El Sauzal	API, Muelle	31°53'39.66"	116°42'8.34"	Buoy (metal)	ERG	33,5	15,1	8	2,6
SAU-B-Q-20210326-2	Puerto de El Sauzal	API, Muelle	31°53'39.66"	116°42'8.34"	Buoy (metal)	ERG	33,5	15,1	8	2,6

Table 1 continued

SAU-B-Q-20210326-3	Puerto de El Sauzal	API, Muelle	31°53'39.66"	116°42'8.34"	Buoy (metal)	ERG	33,5	15,1	8	2,6
SAU-B-Q-20210326-4	Puerto de El Sauzal	API, Muelle	31°53'39.66"	116°42'8.34"	Buoy (metal)	ERG	33,5	15,1	8	2,6
SAU-S-20210326-1	Puerto de El Sauzal	API, Muelle	31°53'39.66"	116°42'8.34"	Buoy (metal)	ERG	33,5	15,1	8	2,6
SJD-A-Q-3-20210314	San José del Cabo	Marina Cabo San Lucas	22°52'55"	109°54'37"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	JALG, MEGG, GGG & CCT	N/D	ND	ND	ND
SNF-S-20210510-1	San Felipe	Platform of totoaba pens	31°02'35.7"	114°48'6.46"	Pneumatic tyre	EAEM & JNGL	36,5	24,6	8	6,7
TEAC-S-20210510-2	Teacapán	Muelle turístico	22°32'20"	105°44' 33"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	MATH	N/D	ND	ND	ND
TOP-A-Q-20210406-1	Topolobampo	Marina Palmira Topolobampo	25°35'57"	109°3'29"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	MATH	35	26	ND	ND
TOP-A-Q-20210406-2	Topolobampo	Marina Palmira Topolobampo	25°35'57"	109°3'29"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	MATH	35	26	ND	ND
TOP-A-Q-20210406-3	Topolobampo	Marina Palmira Topolobampo	25°35'57"	109°3'29"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	MATH	35	26	ND	ND
TOP-A-Q-20210407-4	Topolobampo	Marina Palmira Topolobampo	25°35'59.26"	109°3'28.83"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	MATH	35	26	ND	ND
TOP-A-Q-20210407-5	Topolobampo	Marina Palmira Topolobampo	25°35'59.26"	109°3'28.83"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	MATH	35	26	ND	ND
TOP-A-Q-20210407-6	Topolobampo	Marina Palmira Topolobampo	25°35'59.26"	109°3'28.83"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	MATH	35	26	ND	ND
TOP-A-Q-20210408-7	Topolobampo	Marina Palmira Topolobampo	25°36'1.29"	109°3'29.49"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	MATH	35	26	ND	ND

Table 1 continued

TOP-A-Q-20210408-8	Topolobampo	Marina Palmira Topolobampo	25°36'1.29"	109°3'29.49"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	MATH	35	26	ND	ND
TOP-A-Q-20210408-9	Topolobampo	Marina Palmira Topolobampo	25°36'1.29"	109°3'29.49"	Floating dock (fiberglass covered with a thin layer of concrete)	MATH	35	26	ND	ND

RESULTS

Systematic section

Sabellidae Latreille, 1825

Acromegalomma Gil & Nishi, 2017

Acromegalomma coloratum (Chamberlin, 1919)

(Figs 1–2)

Potamilla clara Chamberlin, 1919: 20. *Potamilla colorata* Chamberlin, 1919: 21. *Megalomma coloratum*.— Knight-Jones 1997: 318, Figs 2M–T.— Tovar-Hernández et al. 2009b: 326–327, Figs 2c, g, 3e–f, 4f–g.— Tovar-Hernández & Carrera-Parra 2011: 25–31, Figs 7A–L, 8A, 9A–S, 10A–B, 28B, 29B.

Acromegalomma coloratum.— Gil & Nishi 2017: 137.— Palma-Neri & Bastida-Zavala 2024: 140–141, Fig. 11C–D.

Material examined. Southern California Bight ecoregion, BAJA CALIFORNIA, Municipio de Ensenada, Puerto de El Sauzal: UANL-8190, SAU-A-Q-20210326-1 (3 spec); UANL-8191, SAU-A-Q-20210326-2 (6 spec); UANL-8192, SAU-A-Q-20210326-3 (2 spec); UANL-8193, SAU-A-Q-20210326-4 (6 spec); UANL-8194, SAU-A-Q-20210326-5 (3 spec). Cortezian ecoregion, SINALOA, Municipio de Ahome, Topolobampo, Marina Palmira: UANL-8195, TOP-A-Q-20210407-4 (1 spec); UANL-8196, TOP-A-Q-20210407-5 (2 spec); UANL-8197, TOP-A-Q-20210407-6 (1 spec); Municipio de Mazatlán, Marina Mazatlán: UANL-8198, MZT-A-Q-20210324-1 (4 spec); UANL-8199, MZT-A-Q-20210324-2 (4 spec); UANL-8200, MZT-A-Q-20210324-4 (2 spec); UANL-8201, MZT-A-Q-20210324-5 (3 spec); UANL-8202, MZT-A-Q-20210324-6 (1 spec); UANL-8203, MZT-A-Q-20210324-7 (1 spec); UANL-8204, MZT-S-20210315-1 (7 spec). Puerto de Mazatlán: UANL-8205, MZT-B-Q-20210319-1 (2 spec); UANL-8206, MZT-B-Q-20210319-8 (1 spec). Municipio de Rosario, Teacapán: UANL-8207, TEAC-S-20210510-2 (+1,000 spec). NAYARIT, Municipio de Santiago Ixcuintla, Marismas Nacionales: UANL-8208, MANA-S-20210508-1 (5 spec); UANL-8209, MANA-S-20210521 (14 spec). JALISCO, Municipio de Puerto Vallarta, Puerto Vallarta: UANL-8210, PVA-B-Q-20210419-1 (1 spec), UANL-8211, PVA-B-Q-20210419-4 (2 spec); UANL-8212, PVA-B-Q-20210419-5 (1 spec); UANL-8213, PVA-B-Q-20210419-6 (6 spec); UANL-8214, PVA-B-Q-20210419-7 (2 spec); UANL-8215, PVA-B-Q-20210419-9 (4 spec). Mexican Tropical Pacific ecoregion, COLIMA, Municipio de Manzanillo, Puerto de Manzanillo: UANL-8216, MAN-A-Q-20210429-2 (1 spec).

Diagnosis. Bodies olive green; yellow ventral shields and white spots in dorsal thorax (Fig. 1). Radiolar crowns with bands of brown to purple radioles, alternating with white bands (Fig. 2). Dorsal most pair of radioles pink or yellow in some specimens (Fig. 1–2). Eyes in dorsalmost and fifth dorsal radioles (spherical); dorsal margin of collar fused to faecal groove; a glandular ring on segment 3; thoracic chaetae Type C; abdominal chaetae broadly hooded.

Figure 1. *Acromegalomma coloratum* (Chamberlin, 1919), TEAC-S-20210510-2. A. Life worms showing radiolar crown color variations, B. Red-brown variation, C–D. Green variation, and dorsal and ventral views, respectively. Scale bars: A–D, 3 mm.

Type locality. Laguna Beach (California, USA). No more data available in original description (Chamberlin, 1919).

Distribution. Southern California Bight, Cortezian and Mexican Tropical Pacific ecoregions. From Laguna Beach and Point Dume (California, USA) to Manzanillo (Colima, Mexico).

Ecology. In the present study, *Acromegalomma coloratum* was collected in floating and fixed docks (plastic or concrete, respectively), ropes, metal buoys, plastic rafts, and sclerozoan of oysters attached to dock pilings, not deeper than 1 m, in the following environmental conditions: temperature, 14.6–28.27°C; salinity, 33.5–37;

dissolved oxygen, 2.7–5.085 mgO₂/l; pH 5.1–7.74 (Table 1). In natural substrates from California (USA) and western Mexico, *A. coloratum* has been reported on basaltic rock, among coralline algae and coral debris, in the rocky intertidal and as oyster sclerozoan (Tovar-Hernández & Carrera-Parra, 2011).

On a floating dock in Teacapán (Sinaloa), *A. coloratum* was found reaching high densities (1,037–1,650 ind/m²) among mats of the invasive ascidian *Didemnum perlucidum* Monniot, 1983, both species being dense. For comparison, *A. coloratum* was reported to reach densities of about 4–80 ind/m² on metal buoys from the Mazatlán port, where the dominant species is the invasive species *Branchiomma bairdi* (McIntosh, 1885) (Tovar-Hernández et al. 2009; Tovar-Hernández & Carrera-Parra, 2011). Regenerating branchial crowns were common in samples from El Sauzal (Baja California) and Teacapán (Sinaloa) samples.

Figure 2. *Acromegalomma coloratum* (Chamberlin, 1919), TEAC-S-20210510-2. A. Life worms showing radiolar crown color variations, left red-brown variation, right green variation, B. Green variation, C. Dorsal most radiolar eyes of green variation, D. Red-brown variation, E. Dorsal most radiolar eyes of red-brown variation. Scale bars: A, 3 mm, B, D, 1.5 mm, C, E, 0.5 mm.

Remarks. *Acromegalomma coloratum* is easy to distinguish among the recognized species from the Eastern Tropical Pacific because radiolar eyes are present only in dorsalmost and fifth dorsal radioles and these are spherical (Tovar-Hernández & Carrera-Parra, 2011). For comparison, eyes in *A. splendidum* (Moore, 1905) are spiraled, present in dorsalmost, second or third dorsal radioles. In *A. gesae* (Knight-Jones, 1997), *A. modestum* (de Quatrefages, 1866) and *A. pigmentum* (Reish, 1963) eyes are present in dorsalmost pair only.

Notaulax Tauber, 1879

Notaulax californica (Treadwell, 1906)

(Fig. 3)

Potamilla californica Treadwell, 1906: 1178.

Hypsicomus sp.— Hartman 1942: 133.

Hypsicomus californicus.— Hartman 1956: 258, 262, 270; Hartman 1969: 701–702.

Notaulax californica.— Perkins 1984: 342–343, fig. 31.— Yáñez-Rivera et al. 2020: 24–26, Fig. 12A–C.— Tovar-Hernández et al. 2020: 17–24, fig. 6–9, 10A–F.— Galván-Villa et al. 2023: S2 (table).

Material examined. Cortezian ecoregion, SINALOA, Municipio de Mazatlán, Marina Mazatlán: UANL-8217, MZT-S-20210424-1 (2 spec); UANL-8218, MZT-A-Q-20210324-7 (1 spec). NAYARIT, Municipio de Bahía de Banderas, La Cruz de Huanacastle, Marina Riviera Nayarit: UANL-8219, NAY-A-Q-20210316-4 (1 spec). JALISCO, Municipio de Puerto Vallarta, Puerto Vallarta: UANL-8220, PVA-S-20210325-2 (3 spec).

Diagnosis. Radiolar crown with basal half translucent-whitish; distal half orange with rows of black ocelli located at three quarters of radiolar crown length (Fig. 3). Ventral margin of collar incised, forming rounded lappets (Fig. 3). Short bands of radiolar ocelli (each band as long as the space of 4–6 pinnules), ocelli distributed in single rows of 5–16 ocelli, eye bands located at three quarters of the radiolar crown length (Fig. 3).

Type locality. Monterey Bay (California, USA). No more data available in original description (Treadwell, 1906).

Distribution. Northern California, Cortezian and Mexican Tropical Pacific ecoregions. From Monterey Bay (California, USA) to Manzanillo (Colima, Mexico).

Ecology. In the present study, *Notaulax californica* was collected in floating docks and ropes not deeper than 1 m, in the following environmental conditions: temperature, 18–23.5°C; salinity, 35–37; pH 6.3–6.7 (Table 1). In natural substrates from western Mexico, *N. californica* has been reported on dead coral and coral debris (Tovar-Hernández et al. 2020, Yáñez-Rivera et al. 2020).

Remarks. *Notaulax californica* is easy to distinguish among the recognized species from the Eastern Tropical Pacific because the radiolar ocelli are distributed in single rows of five ocelli to 16 ocelli located at three quarters of the radiolar crown length. In *N. punctulata* Tovar-Hernández, García-Garza & de León-González, 2020 ocelli are distributed in single rows of 24 ocelli each, located at the middle of the radiolar crown length. In *N. nigroincrustedata* Tovar-Hernández, García-Garza & de León-González, 2020 radiolar ocelli are distributed in oval groups of 26–30 ocelli each, located at the middle of the radiolar crown length. Other differences related to the shape of collar and presence of interramal eyespots on abdominal segments can be consulted in Tovar-Hernández et al. (2020).

Paradialychone Tovar-Hernández, 2008

Paradialychone ecaudata (Moore, 1923)

(Fig. 4)

Jasmineira ecaudata Moore, 1923: 246–248.

Chone ecaudata.— Hartman 1942: 135; 1969: 663.— Berkeley & Berkeley 1950: 76; 1952: 124.— Tovar-

Hernández 2007: 525–530, Figs 4–6, 19A.

Chone minuta Hartman, 1944: 280–281, Pt. 23, Figs 50–52, Pt. 24, Figs 59, 60 *vide* Banse 1972: 474.

Paradialychone ecaudata.— Tovar-Hernández 2008: 2221.

Figure 3. *Notaulax californica* (Treadwell, 1906), MZT-S-20210424-1. A. Radiolar crown, lateral view, B. Radioles, arrow pointing to radiolar eyes, C. thorax, dorsal view, D. same, latero-ventral view. Scale bars: A, 1 mm, B, 0.3 mm, C, 1.5 mm, D, 0.5 mm. Abbreviation: pm palmate membrane.

Material examined. Southern California Bight ecoregion, BAJA CALIFORNIA, Municipio de Ensenada, Puerto de Ensenada: UANL-8221, ENS-A-Q-20210315-1 (1 spec); UANL-8222, ENS-A-Q-20210315-6 (1 spec); UANL-8223, ENS-B-Q-20210315-4 (1 spec); UANL-8224, ENS-B-Q-20210315-6 (3 spec); UANL-8225, ENS-B-Q-20210315-7 (2 spec); UANL-8226, ENS-B-Q-20210315-9 (1 spec); UANL-8227, ENS-S-20210315-1 (1 spec); UANL-8228, ENS-S-20210315-2 (3 spec). Puerto de El Sauzal: UANL-8229, SAU-A-Q-20210326-1 (17 spec); UANL-8230, SAU-A-Q-20210326-2 (7 spec); UANL-8231, SAU-A-Q-20210326-3 (82 spec); UANL-8232, SAU-A-Q-20210326-4 (1 spec); UANL-8233, SAU-B-Q-20210326-1 (20 spec); UANL-8234, SAU-B-Q-20210326-2 (31 spec); UANL-8235, SAU-B-Q-20210326-3 (18 spec); UANL-8236, SAU-B-Q-20210326-4 (2 spec); UANL-8237, SAU-S-20210326-1 (6 spec).

Diagnosis. Ventral shield of collar swollen, horseshoe-shaped, 1.5 times wider than long. Radiolar flanges broad. Radiolar tips long. Anterior peristomial ring lobe distally entire, triangular, with a short tip exposed beyond

collar margin. Glandular ridge on chaetiger 2 narrow all around (Fig. 4). Paleate chaetae with long mucro.

Type locality. Off Santa Cruz Island (California, USA), 69–82 m depth, on mud and coarse gray sand (Moore, 1923).

Distribution. Southern California Bight ecoregion, in Dillon Beach (California, USA) and Ensenada (Baja California, Mexico). Possibly, extending to Guerrero state (Rodríguez-Valencia, 2004).

Figure 4. *Paradialychone ecaudata* (Moore, 1923), SAU-A-Q-20210326-3. A, C. Bodies, lateral view, B. Collar and crown, ventral view, D. Collar and crown, dorsal view, E. Anterior peristomial ring and glandular ridge on chaetiger 2, lateral view (crown removed), F. Radiolar crown. All stained with methyl green. Abbreviations: aprl (anterior peristomial ring lobe), gr2 (glandular ridge on chaetiger 2). Scale bars: A–B, D, F, 1 mm, C, 2 mm, E, 0.3 mm.

Ecology. In the present study, *Paradialychone ecaudata* was collected as fouling in fixed (concrete) and floating docks (plastic), buoys (plastic and metal) and metal hull of ship of ports of western coast of Baja California

(Ensenada and El Sauzal) not deeper than 1 m, in the following environmental conditions: temperature, 14.6–15.4°C; salinity, 33.5–33.9; dissolved oxygen, 2.6–7.3 mgO₂/l; pH 7.59–8.161 (Table 1). In natural substrates from California (USA) and western Mexico, *Paradialychone ecaudata* is commonly found in intertidal soft bottoms, holdfast of algae and compound ascidians (Rodríguez-Valencia 2004: as *Chone ecaudata* [sic]; Tovar-Hernández 2007).

Remarks. Among the recognized species from the Eastern Tropical Pacific *P. ecaudata* and *P. paramollis* (Tovar-Hernández, 2007) have the ventral shield of collar horseshoe-shaped (1.5 times wider than long in *P. ecaudata*; as wide as long in *P. paramollis*), but in the former the anterior peristomial ring is exposed beyond collar margins (not exposed in *P. paramollis*).

Parasabella pallida Moore, 1923

(Fig. 5–6)

Parasabella pallida Moore, 1923: 241, 242.— Tovar-Hernández & Harris 2010: 15.— Keppel et al. 2020: 110–113, fig. 8.— Bastida-Zavala et al. 2016: 407–408, figs. 2, 10D.— Tovar-Hernández et al. 2019: 5, fig. 2B.— Yáñez-Rivera et al. 2020: 26–27, fig. 12D–F.— Galván-Villa et al. 2023: S2 (table).

Sabella media.— Hartman 1944: 285 [in part, not pl. 23, fig. 42] *fide* Perkins, 1984. *Demonax medius*.— Hartman 1969: 675, 676 [in part, not figs 1–5] *fide* Perkins, 1984. *Demonax pallidus*.— Perkins 1984: 313–315, figs 15–16.— Tovar-Hernández et al. 2009b: 325–326, figs 2b, f, 3c–d, 4c–e.

Material examined. Cortezian ecoregion, BAJA CALIFORNIA, Municipio de San Felipe, Puerto de San Felipe: UANL-8238, SNF-S-20210510-1 (2 spec); Municipio de San Quintín, Bahía de los Ángeles: UANL-8239, BLA-S-20210511-1 (1 spec); UANL-8240, BLA-S-20210511-2 (2 spec). BAJA CALIFORNIA SUR, Municipio de La Paz, Marina Fonatur La Paz, UANL-8241, FLP-S-2-20210312 (1 spec); Municipio de Los Cabos, Marina Cabo San Lucas, UANL-8242, SJD-A-Q-3-20210314 (1 spec); Municipio de Mulegé, Marina Santa Rosalía, UANL-8243, SAR-A-Q-20210309-1 (1 spec). SINALOA, Municipio de Ahome, Topolobampo, Marina Palmira: UANL-8244, TOP-A-Q-20210406-1 (3 spec); UANL-8245, TOP-A-Q-20210406-2 (1 spec); UANL-8246, TOP-A-Q-20210406-3 (1 specimen); UANL-8247, TOP-A-Q-20210407-6 (1 spec); UANL-8248, TOP-A-Q-20210408-7 (1 spec); UANL-8249, TOP-A-Q-20210408-8 (1 spec); UANL-8250, TOP-A-Q-20210408-9 (1 spec). Municipio de Mazatlán, Marina Mazatlán: UANL-8251, MZT-A-Q-20210324-3 (1 spec) UANL-8252, MZT-A-Q-20210324-5 (2 spec); UANL-8253, MZT-S-20210424-1 (1 spec). Puerto de Mazatlán: UANL-8254, MZT-B-Q-20210319-2 (1 spec); UANL-8255, MZT-B-Q-20210319-7 (1 spec). NAYARIT, Municipio de Santiago Ixcuintla, Marismas Nacionales: UANL-8256, MANA-S-20210508-1 (32 spec); UANL-8257, MANA-S-20210521 (42 spec). JALISCO, Municipio de Puerto Vallarta, Puerto Vallarta: UANL-8258, PVA-B-Q-20210419-6 (2 spec); UANL-8259, PVA-B-Q-20210419-9 (4 spec).

Diagnosis. Radioles with brown spots (Fig. 5). Bare, digitiform radiolar tips (not pinnulate). Inferior group of thoracic notochaetae with the lateral hoods narrower than the shaft width, progressively tapering to the distal tip. Dorsal lips with a broad, rounded base formed by lateral lamellae, a mid-rib support and a short size-distal filament (ear-shaped lip) (Fig. 6).

Type locality. off Santa Cruz Lighthouse, 18 m depth, fine gray sand and rock (Moore, 1923).

Distribution. Northern California, Cortezian and Mexican Tropical Pacific Ecoregions. From San Francisco and Santa Cruz (California, USA) to Manzanillo (Colima, Mexico).

Ecology. In the present study, *Parasabella pallida* was collected as biofouler in a platform of Totoaba pens, in a raft of plastic, ropes, floating docks, plastic buoys and sclerozoan of oysters attached to dock pilings not deeper than 1 m, in the following environmental conditions: temperature, 17.2–30.38°C; salinity, 30–37; dissolved oxygen, 6.7–11.1 mgO₂/l; pH 5.1–8.27 (Table 1). In natural substrates from California (USA) and western Mexico, *P. pallida* has been reported in fine gray sand and rock, and coralline rock (Moore, 1923; Yáñez-Rivera et al. 2020).

Remarks. *Parasabella pallida* and *P. rugosa* have typical spotted radioles (Figs 5A–B, 7A–B), but the former has bare, digitiform radiolar tips (not pinnulate) (Fig. 5D), whereas in *P. rugosa* radiolar tips are pinnulate (pinnules extend to the radiolar tips) (Fig. 7D). Moreover, the inferior group of thoracic notochaetae (broadly hooded) are different in both species. In *P. pallida*, the lateral hoods are narrower than the shaft width, progressively tapering to the distal tip (Fig. 5E–F), whereas in *P. rugosa*, the hoods are as broad as shaft width, then progressively tapering to the distal tip (Fig. 7E–F). Besides, in *P. pallida*, the dorsal lips have a broad, rounded base formed by lateral lamellae, a mid-rib support and a short size-distal filament (ear-shaped lip) (Fig. 6A–F), whereas *P. rugosa* has triangular and tapered lips, with mid-rib support and lateral lamellae that narrow end as a long filament (Fig. 7C).

Figure 5. *Parasabella pallida* Moore, 1923, PVA-B-Q-20210419-9. A) Thorax and crown, dorsal view; B. Same, ventral view; C. Same, lateral view; D. Radiolar tip; E–F. broadly hooded thoracic chaetae. Scale bars: A–C, 1.3 mm, C, 0.2 mm, D–E. 400 x magnification.

Parasabella rugosa (Moore, 1904)

(Fig. 7)

Distylia rugosa Moore, 1904: 499–501, pl. 38, figs. 38–41.

Distylidia rugosa.— Hartman 1961: 129; 1969: 667 (*in part*).

Sabella (*Demonax*) *media*.— Banse 1979: 878–880.

Demonax rugosus.— Perkins 1984: 304–307, figs 9–10.

Parasabella rugosa.— Tovar-Hernández & Harris 2010: 15.

Material examined. Southern California Bight ecoregion. BAJA CALIFORNIA, Municipio de Ensenada, Puerto de Ensenada: UANL-8260, ENS-A-Q-20210315-2 (2 spec); UANL-8261, ENS-A-Q-20210315-7 (10 spec). Puerto de El Sauzal: UANL-8262, SAU-B-Q-20210326-1 (1 spec); UANL-8263, SAU-A-Q-20210326-3 (2 spec).

Diagnosis. Radioles with brown spots. Radiolar tips pinnulate (pinnules extend to the radiolar tips). Inferior group of thoracic notochaetae with lateral hoods as broad as shaft width, then progressively tapering to the distal tip (Fig. 7). Dorsal lips triangular and tapered, with mid-rib support and lateral lamellae that narrow end as a long filament (Fig. 7).

Type locality. San Diego (California, USA). No more data available in original description (Moore, 1904).

Distribution. Southern California Bight ecoregion. San Diego (California, USA) and Ensenada (Baja California, Mexico).

Ecology. In the present study, *Parasabella rugosa* was collected as fouler of fixed and floating docks, not deeper than 1 m, in the following environmental conditions: temperature, 14.6–15.4°C; salinity, 33.5–33.9; dissolved oxygen, 2.6–7.7 ml O₂/l; pH 7.66–7.973 (Table 1). Formal records of *P. rugosa* in natural substrates from California (USA) are unknown.

Remarks. The present report constitute the first record of *P. rugosa* for Mexico.

Figure 7. *Parasabella rugosa* (Moore, 1904), SAU-A-Q-2021-0326-3. A. Thorax and crown, latero-dorsal view; B. Same, ventral view; C. Left dorsal and ventral lips; D. Radiolar tip; E–F. broadly hooded thoracic chaetae. Scale bars: A–B, 1 mm, C, 0.5 mm, D, 0.2 mm, E–F, 400 x magnification. Abbreviations: dl (dorsal lip), vl (ventral lip).

Pseudobranchiomma Jones, 1962

Pseudobranchiomma schizogenica Tovar-Hernández & Dean, 2014

(Fig. 8)

Pseudobranchiomma schizogenica in Tovar-Hernández & Dean, 2014: 936–944, figs. 1–5.— Keppel et al. 2019: 67–68, fig. 6.— Tovar-Hernández et al. 2019: 5, fig. 2C.— Yáñez-Rivera et al. 2020: 27–28, fig. 13A–C.— Galván-Villa et al. 2023: S2 (table).

Material examined. Cortezian ecoregion, BAJA CALIFORNIA SUR, Municipio de La Paz, Marina Cantamar La Paz: UANL-8264, CLP-A-Q-20210313-2 (4 spec). NAYARIT, Municipio de Bahía de Banderas, La Cruz de Huanacastle, Marina Riviera Nayarit: UANL-8265, NAY-A-Q-20210315-1 (89 spec); UANL-8266, NAY-A-Q-20210315-2 (42 spec); UANL-8267, NAY-A-Q-20210316-6 (39 spec); UANL-8268, NAY-A-Q-20210317-7 (8 spec); UANL-8269, NAY-A-Q-20210317-8 (12 spec); UANL-8270, NAY-A-Q-20210317-9 (3 spec).

Figure 8. *Pseudobranchiomma schizogenica* Tovar-Hernández & Dean, 2014, NAY-A-Q-20210315-1. A. Body, lateral view, B) Thorax, dorsal view, C. Anterior peristomial ring lobe and thoracic segments, lateral view, D. Thorax and crown, ventral view, E. Anterior peristomial ring lobe and thoracic segments, dorso-lateral view, F. Radioles showing flanges as indicated in arrows. Abbreviations: aprl, anterior peristomial ring lobe. Scale bars: A–F, 0.5 mm.

Diagnosis. Bodies with dark spots and interrampal, purple eyes (Fig. 8). Radioles with short, digitiform serrations along the entire radiolar length (Fig. 8). Lateral margins of collar oblique, covering anterior peristomial ring. Ventral shield of collar trapezoidal; divided in two halves: anterior half Y-shaped, posterior half W-shaped. Thoracic superior chaetae with hoods narrower than shafts. Thoracic inferior chaetae spinelike with hoods as width as shafts. Abdominal neurochaetae spinelike with hoods narrower than shafts (about a half width of shaft). Paired patches of cilia in ventral lappets of collar, thoracic and abdominal shields.

Type locality. Club de Yates Palmira, La Paz, Baja California Sur, Mexico, floating dock fouling, 50 cm depth.

Distribution. Cortezian, Mexican Tropical Pacific and Eastern Galapagos Islands ecoregions. From La Paz (Baja California Sur, Mexico) to Galápagos Archipelago (Ecuador).

Ecology. In the present study, *Pseudobranchiomma schizogenica* was collected as fouler of floating docks not deeper than 1 m, in the following environmental conditions: temperature, 22.22–24.66°C; salinity, 35–38; pH 7.1–7.4 (Table 1). In natural substrates from western Mexico, *P. schizogenica* was reported on rock (Yáñez-Rivera et al. 2020).

Remarks. *Pseudobranchiomma schizogenica* was originally described from dock fouling in shallow water in the southern Gulf of California, but its origin is still unknown. Capa & Murray (2016) reported populations of *P. cf. schizogenica* in Australia and Hawaii, and it was also found in Galápagos by Keppel et al. (2019). Surprisingly, the species hasn't been reported in Mazatlán yet.

Pseudopotamilla Bush, 1905
Pseudopotamilla sp. Manzanillo
(Fig. 9)

Material examined. Mexican Tropical Pacific ecoregion, COLIMA, Municipio de Manzanillo, Puerto de Manzanillo: UANL-8271, MAN-A-Q-20210429-7 (1 spec); UANL-8272, MAN-A-Q-20210429-9 (1 spec).

Diagnosis. Eyes absent in radiole 1, present in basal half of radioles 2, 3 and 4 (one eye per radiole). A dorsal glandular ridge on intersegmental division between the collar and the second chaetiger. Ventral shield of collar entire. Ventral lappets of collar low. Thoracic tori reaching ventral shields margins (Fig. 9).

Ecology. In the present study, *Pseudopotamilla* sp. was collected as fouler in a fixed dock (concrete) not deeper than 1 m, in following environmental conditions: temperature, 20.7–20.75°C; salinity, 35.18–35.22; dissolved oxygen, 4.167–4.545 ml O₂/ (Table 1).

Distribution. Mexican Tropical Pacific ecoregion. Only found in Manzanillo (Colima, Mexico).

Remarks. Only two specimens were found as dock fouling belonging to the same species, but with distinctive features from other species of *Pseudopotamilla* nominal species: (I) a peculiar dorsal glandular ridge on intersegmental division between the collar and the second chaetiger (Fig. 8A, C–D) (not seen or reported in any species of *Pseudopotamilla*), (II) an entire ventral shield (Fig. 8B, F), (III) ventral lappets of collar low (Fig. 8B, F), (IV) thoracic tori reaching ventral shields margins (Fig. 8F), and (V) three radiolar eyes in the basal half of radiolar crown with the following formulae: X111XX, which is counted from dorsal-most radiole towards the ventral-most radiole on the right branchial lobe; and means that the right side of the crown has six radioles: eyes absent in radiole 1 (dorsal-most radiole), one eye in radioles 2, 3 and 4, and radioles 5 and 6 without eyes. However, as demonstrated for *P. socialis* Hartman, 1944 (Tovar-Hernández et al. 2025, under revision), the radiolar eyes formulae are highly variable within a single population. Only one of the two specimens reviewed from Manzanillo preserves the branchial crown. Further specimens are needed to formally describe this taxon as new species.

Figure 9. *Pseudopotamilla* sp. Manzanillo, MAN-A-Q-20210429-9. A, E. Thorax, dorsal view; B, F. Same ventral view; C–D. Detail of dorsal glandular ridge on intersegmental division between collar and second chaetiger; G. Thoracic chaetae; C, E–F. Stained with Shirla Stain A, Arrows points to the dorsal glandular ridge. Scale bars: A–B, 1 mm, C–F, 0.5 mm, G, 40 x magnification.

DISCUSSION

In Mexico 23 species of sabellids have been found as biofoulers on diverse anthropogenic substrates (Table 2); seven of these species are herein reported from the Mexican Pacific. As the sabellid worms are one of the major groups in fouling communities, it is important to have a baseline that recognizes of the different species that form these communities, with special emphasis on non-native species. For the moment, only species of *Branchiomma*, *Pseudobranchiomma*, *Parasabella*, and *Sabella* Linnaeus, 1767 has been confirmed to present a wide distribution in substrates of anthropogenic origin, as result of unintentional introductions and translocations in many areas from the world (del Pasqua et al. 2008, Read et al. 2011, Capa et al. 2013, Capa & Murray 2015, 2016). Except for *Pseudobranchiomma schizogenica*, the rest of the species here reported are presumably native to the Tropical Eastern Pacific and Warm Temperate Northeast Pacific provinces, but additional studies on phylogeography are needed. *Acromegalomma coloratum* reached high densities (up to 1,650 ind/m²) in floating docks in western Mexico, where it was embedded within dense mats of the invasive ascidian *Didemnum perlucidum*. Consequently, it is recommended that studies be conducted on their biology and population ecology. The information generated here would aid in monitoring programs to determine fluctuations in the distribution of these and other species and to evaluate the impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem functioning by non-native fan worms.

Table 2. Records of fan worms (Sabellidae) as biofoulers in Mexico.

<p><i>Acromegalomma carunculatum</i> (Tovar-Hernández & Salazar-Vallejo, 2008)</p> <p>Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bastida-Zavala et al. 2016 (as <i>Megalomma carunculata</i>): Bahía de los Angeles (Baja California), Marina Cantamar La Paz (Baja California Sur), anthropogenic substrates.
<p><i>Acromegalomma circumspectum</i> (Moore, 1923)</p> <p>Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tovar-Hernández et al. 2014: Club de Yates Palmira, La Paz (Baja California Sur), dock fouling.
<p><i>Acromegalomma coloratum</i> (Chamberlin, 1919)</p> <p>Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tovar-Hernández et al. 2009b (as <i>Megalomma colorata</i>): Puerto de Mazatlán (Sinaloa), buoy, dock and hull fouling. • Tovar-Hernández & Carrera-Parra, 2011: Puerto de Mazatlán (Sinaloa), buoy fouling. • Palma-Neri & Bastida-Zavala 2024: Puerto Ángel (Oaxaca), concrete pier piles. • Present study: Puerto de El Sauzal (Baja California), fixed and floating docks; Marina Palmira Topolobampo (Sinaloa), floating dock; Marina Mazatlán (Sinaloa), floating dock; Puerto de Mazatlán (Sinaloa), ropes and metal buoys; Teacapán (Sinaloa), floating dock; Reserva de la Biosfera Marismas Nacionales, Boca del Camichín (Nayarit), plastic raft and sclerozoan of oyster attached to dock pilings; Puerto Vallarta (Jalisco), metal buoys; Puerto de Manzanillo (Colima), fixed dock.
<p><i>Acromegalomma gesae</i> (Knight-Jones, 1997)</p> <p>Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Palma-Neri & Bastida-Zavala, 2024: Salina Cruz and Puerto Ángel (Oaxaca), concrete piers.
<p><i>Bispira brunnea</i> (Treadwell, 1917)</p> <p>Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tovar-Hernández & Pineda-Vera, 2008: Arrecife Alacranes (Yucatán), dock fouling.

<p><i>Bispira melanostigma</i> (Schmarda, 1861) Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tovar-Hernández & Salazar-Vallejo, 2006: Majahual (Quintana Roo), dock fouling.
<p><i>Branchiomma bairdi</i> (McIntosh, 1885) Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tovar-Hernández et al. 2009a-b: Puerto de Mazatlán (Sinaloa), metal buoy, fixed and floating docks and hull fouling. • Tovar-Hernández et al. 2014: Club de Yates Palmira Topolobampo, API Topolobampo, Embarcadero Topolobampo, Muelle Pemex Topolobampo (Sinaloa); API Guaymas, Marina Fonatur Guaymas, Marina Real San Carlos (Sonora); API La Paz, Marina La Paz, Club de Yates Palmira La Paz (Baja California Sur), buoy, dock and hull fouling. Oyster farm, Ahome (Sinaloa), nets, cages and trays fouling, and sclerozoan of oysters. • Bastida-Zavala et al. 2016: Bahía de los Angeles (Baja California); Marina Santa Rosalía, Marina Cantamar La Paz, Marina Palmira La Paz, Marina Puerto Los Cabos, Marina Cabo San Lucas (Baja California Sur), anthropogenic substrates; Laguna Corralero (Oaxaca), dock and hull fouling. • del Pasqua et al. 2018: Mazatlán (Sinaloa) and Veracruz (Veracruz), buoy and dock fouling. • Ramos-Morales et al. 2024: Chahué Marina, Huatulco (Oaxaca), PVC plates fouling. • Palma-Neri & Bastida-Zavala, 2024: Salina Cruz and Marina Chahué (Oaxaca), fishing pier and floating concrete pier.
<p><i>Branchiomma coheni</i> Tovar-Hernández & Knight-Jones, 2006 Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keppel et al. 2015: Mazatlán and Topolobampo (Sinaloa); San Carlos (Sonora), La Paz (Baja California Sur), dock fouling.
<p><i>Branchiomma conspersum</i> (Ehlers, 1887) Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tovar-Hernández & Knight-Jones, 2006: Celestún (Yucatán), dock fouling.
<p><i>Branchiomma curtum</i> (Ehlers, 1901) Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tovar-Hernández & Knight-Jones, 2006: Isla Contoy (Quintana Roo), dock fouling.
<p><i>Branchiomma</i> sp. Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Galván-Villa et al. 2023: Bahía de Santiago, Manzanillo (Colima), submerged shipwreck.
<p><i>Notaulax californica</i> (Treadwell, 1906) Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tovar-Hernández et al. 2020: La Paz (Baja California Sur), Topolobampo and Mazatlán (Sinaloa), buoy fouling. • Present study: Marina Mazatlán (Sinaloa), floating dock; Marina Riviera Nayarit (Nayarit), floating dock; Puerto Vallarta (Jalisco), floating dock.
<p><i>Notaulax midoculi</i> (Hoagland, 1919) Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tovar-Hernández & Salazar-Vallejo, 2006: Puerta Maya, Cozumel (Quintana Roo), dock fouling.

<p><i>Notaulax nigroincrustedata</i> Tovar-Hernández, García-Garza & de León-González, 2020</p> <p>Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tovar-Hernández et al. 2020: La Paz (Baja California Sur), dock and hull fouling.
<p><i>Notaulax punctulata</i> Tovar-Hernández, García-Garza & de León-González, 2020</p> <p>Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tovar-Hernández et al. 2020: Acapulco (Guerrero), dock fouling and sclerozoan of oyster attached to dock pilings.
<p><i>Paradialychone ecaudata</i> (Moore, 1923)</p> <p>Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Present study: puerto de Ensenada (Baja California), fixed and floating docks, hull ship, plastic and metal buoys; puerto de El Sauzal (Baja California), fixed and floating docks, metal buoy.
<p><i>Parasabella</i> cf. <i>lacunosa</i></p> <p>Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ramos-Morales et al. 2024: Chahué Marina, Huatulco (Oaxaca), PVC plates fouling.
<p><i>Parasabella pallida</i> Moore, 1923</p> <p>Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tovar-Hernández et al. 2009b (as <i>Demonax</i>): Mazatlán (Sinaloa), buoy, dock and hull fouling. • Bastida-Zavala et al. 2016: Puerto Escondido (Baja California Sur), anthropogenic substrates. • Tovar-Hernández et al. 2019: API La Paz (Baja California Sur), hull fouling; Marina La Paz (Baja California Sur), dock fouling. • Galván-Villa et al. 2023: Bahía de Santiago, Manzanillo (Colima), submerged shipwreck. • Present study: San Felipe (Baja California), pneumatic tyre and platform for totoaba pens; Bahía de los Angeles (Baja California), plastic buoy; Santa Rosalía (Baja California Sur), floating dock; Marina Cabo San Lucas (Baja California Sur), floating dock; Marina Fonatur La Paz (Baja California Sur), floating dock; Marina Palmira Topolobampo (Sinaloa), floating dock; Marina Mazatlán (Sinaloa), floating dock; Mazatlán (Sinaloa), metal buoys; Marismas Nacionales, Boca del Camichín (Nayarit), plastic raft and sclerozoan of oyster attached to dock pilings; Puerto Vallarta (Jalisco), metal buoys.
<p><i>Parasabella rugosa</i> (Moore, 1904)</p> <p>Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Present study: puerto de Ensenada (Baja California), floating and fixed docks; puerto de El Sauzal (Baja California), metal buoy.
<p><i>Pseudobranchiomma punctata</i> (Treadwell, 1906)</p> <p>Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bastida-Zavala et al. 2016: Marina Palmira La Paz and Marina Los Cabos (Baja California Sur), anthropogenic substrates.
<p><i>Pseudobranchiomma schizogenica</i> Tovar-Hernández & Dean, 2014</p> <p>Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tovar-Hernández & Dean, 2014: Club de Yates Palmira La Paz (Baja California Sur), dock fouling. • Tovar-Hernández et al. 2019: API La Paz (Baja California Sur): ship fouling; Marina La Paz and Club de Yates Palmira La Paz (Baja California Sur), dock fouling. • Galván-Villa et al. 2023: Bahía de Santiago, Manzanillo (Colima), submerged shipwreck. • Present study: Marina Cantamar La Paz (Baja California Sur), floating dock; Marina Riviera Nayarit

(Nayarit), floating dock.
<i>Pseudopotamilla socialis</i> (Hartman, 1944) Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tovar-Hernández et al. 2019: API La Paz (Baja California Sur), hull ship; Marina La Paz (Baja California Sur), dock fouling.
<i>Pseudopotamilla</i> sp. Sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Present study: puerto de Manzanillo (Colima), fixed dock.

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LITERATURE CITED

- Banse, K. 1972. Redescription of some species of *Chone* Kröyer and *Euchone* Malmgren, and three new species (Sabellidae, Polychaeta).— Fishery Bulletin and Wildlife Service, USA Department of Interior 70: 459–495.
- . 1979. Sabellidae (Polychaeta) principally from the northeast Pacific Ocean.— Journal of the Fisheries Research Board of Canada 36(8): 869–882.
- Bastida-Zavala, J.R., A.S. Rodríguez-Buelna, J.A. de León-González, K.A. Camacho-Cruz & I. Carmona. 2016. New records of sabellids and serpulids (Polychaeta: Sabellidae, Serpulidae) from the Tropical Eastern Pacific.— Zootaxa 4148 (3): 401–457.
- Berkeley, E., & C. Berkeley. 1950. Notes on Polychaeta from the coast of western Canada, IV Polychaeta Sedentaria.— Annals and Magazine of Natural History 3: 50–69.
- Bush, K.J. 1905. Tubicolous annelids of the tribes Sabellides and Serpulides from the Pacific Ocean.— Harriman Alaska Expedition 12: 169–355.
- Capa, M., & A. Murray. 2015. Integrative taxonomy of *Parasabella* and *Sabellomma* (Sabellidae: Annelida) from Australia: description of new species, indication of cryptic diversity, and translocation of some species out of their natural distribution range.— Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society 175: 764–811.
- , & ———. 2016. Combined morphological and molecular data unveils relationships of *Pseudobranchiomma* (Sabellidae, Annelida) and reveals higher diversity of this intriguing group of fan worms in Australia, including potentially introduced species.— ZooKeys 622: 1–36.
- , E. Kupriyanova, J.M.M. Nogueira, A. Bick & M.A. Tovar-Hernández. 2021. Fanworms: Yesterday, Today and Tomorrow.— Diversity 13 (3): 130.
- , J. Pons & P. Hutchings. 2013. Cryptic diversity, intraspecific phenetic plasticity and recent geographical translocations in *Branchiomma* (Sabellidae, Annelida).— Zoologica Scripta 42 (6): 637–655.
- Chamberlin, R.V. 1919. New polychaetous annelids from Laguna Beach, California.— Pomona College Journal of Entomology and Zoology 11 (1): 1–23.
- De Quatrefages, A. 1866. Histoire Naturelle des Annelés Marins et d'Eau Douce. Annélides et Géphyriens. Paris: Librairie Encyclopédique de Roret.
- Del Pasqua, M.D., A. Schulze, M.A. Tovar-Hernández, E. Keppel, M. Lezzi, M.C. Gambi, & A. Giangrande. 2018.

- Clarifying the taxonomic status of the alien species *Branchiomma bairdi* and *Branchiomma boholense* (Annelida: Sabellidae) using molecular and morphological evidence.– PLoS ONE 13 (5): e0197104.
- Ehlers, E. 1887. Reports on the results of dredging, under the direction of L. F. Pourtalès, during the years 1868-1870, and of Alexander Agassiz, in the Gulf of Mexico (1877-78), and in the Caribbean Sea (1878-79), in the U.S. Coast Survey steamer "Blake", Lieut-Com. C. D. Sigsbee, U.S.N. and Commander J. R. Bartlett, U.S.N., commanding. XXXI. Report on the Annelids.– Memoirs of the Museum of Comparative Zoology at Harvard College 15: vi & 335 pp.
- . 1901. Die Anneliden der Sammlung Plate, In: Plate, L. (1902). Fauna chilensis. Abhandlungen zur Kenntniss der Zoologie Chiles nach den Sammlungen von Dr. L. Plate. Zweiter Band.– Zoologische Jahrbücher Supplementband 2 (2): 251–272.
- Galván-Villa, C.M., M.A. Tovar-Hernández, F.A. Rodríguez-Zaragoza, M.C. Esqueda-González, J. Sánchez-Rodríguez & E. Ríos-Jara. 2023. Effect of the alien octocoral *Carijoa riisei* on benthic fauna assemblages on natural and artificial substrates.– Marine Ecology 44 (4): e12756.
- Gil, J., & E. Nishi. 2017. Nomenclatural checklist for *Acromegalomma* species (Annelida, Sabellidae), a *nomen novum* replacement for the junior homonym *Megalomma* Johansson, 1926.– ZooKeys 677: 131–150.
- Gmelin, J.F. 1791. Vermes. In: Gmelin J.F. (Ed.) Caroli a Linnaei Systema Naturae per Regna Tria Naturae, Ed. 13. Tome 1(6). G.E. Beer, Lipsiae [Leipzig]. pp. 3021–3910. Systema Naturae. Linnaeus (ed.). Ed. 13. 1: pars. 6
- Hartman, O. 1942. The identity of some marine annelid worms in the United States National Museum.– Proceedings of the United States National Museum 93 (3142): 101–140.
- . 1944. Polychaetous annelids from California, including the descriptions of two new genera and nine new species.– Allan Hancock Pacific Expeditions 10 (2): 239–307.
- . 1956. Polychaetes annelids erected by Treadwell, 1891 to 1948, together with a brief chronology.– Bulletin of the American Museum of Natural History 109 (2): 239–310.
- . 1961. Polychaetous annelids from California.– Allan Hancock Pacific Expeditions, 25: 1–226.
- . 1969. Atlas of the sedentariate polychaetous annelids from California. Allan Hancock Foundation, University of Southern California. Los Angeles, 802 pp.
- Jones, M.L. 1962. On some polychaetous annelids from Jamaica, the West Indies.– Bulletin of the American Museum of Natural History 124 (5): 169–212.
- Keppel, E., I. Keith, G.M. Ruiz, & J.T. Carlton. 2019. New records of native and non-indigenous polychaetes (Annelida: Polychaeta) in the Galapagos Islands.– Aquatic Invasions 14.
- , M.A. Tovar-Hernández & G. Ruiz. 2015. First record of *Branchiomma coheni* (Polychaeta: Sabellidae) along the US East coast and update of non indigenous species.– Zootaxa 4058 (4): 499–518.
- , ———, & ———, 2018. New records of the non-indigenous species *Branchiomma bairdi* and *B. conspersum* (Polychaeta: Sabellidae) on the Pacific coast of North America.– BioInvasions Records 7 (3): 229–236.
- , G.M. Ruiz, & M.A. Tovar-Hernández. 2020. Re-description of *Parasabella fullo* (Grube, 1878) (Polychaeta: Sabellidae) and diagnostic characteristics for detection in California.– The European Zoological Journal 87 (1): 105–115.
- Knight-Jones, P. 1997. Two new species of *Megalomma* (Sabellidae) from Sinai and New Zealand with redescription of some types and a new genus.– Bulletin of Marine Science 60 (2): 313–323.
- , T. Darbyshire, M.E. Petersen, & M.A. Tovar-Hernández. 2017. What is *Pseudopotamilla reniformis* (Sabellidae)? Comparisons of populations from Britain, Iceland and Canada with comments on *Eudistylia* and *Schizobranchia*.– Zootaxa 4254 (2): 201–220.
- Kölliker, A. 1858. Ueber Kopfkiemer mit Augen an den Kiemen.– Zeitschrift für wissenschaftliche Zoologie 9: 536–541.
- Kupriyanova, E., P. Hutchings & E. Wong. 2016. A fully illustrated web-based guide to distinguish native and introduced polychaetes of Australia.– Management of Biological Invasions 7 (3): 305–312.
- , M.A. Tovar-Hernández, G. Mejía, P.R. Jayachandran, I. Brandão & J.A. de León-González. 2024. Confirming the invasion by *Ficopomatus cf. uschakovi* (Annelida, Serpulidae) in Mexico.– Bioinvasions Records 13 (4): 979–991.
- Latreille, P.A. 1825. Familles naturelles du règne animal, exposées succinctement et dans un ordre analytique avec l'indication de leurs genres. Paris. J.B. Baillièrre 1–570.
- Linnaeus, C. 1767. Systema naturae per regna tria naturae: secundum classes, ordines, genera, species, cum characteribus, differentiis, synonymis, locis. Ed. 12. 1., Regnum Animale. 1 & 2. [The system of nature through the three kingdoms of nature: according to classes, orders, genera, species, with characters, differences, synonyms, places. Ed. 12. 1.,

- Animal Kingdom. 1 & 2]. *Holmiae [Stockholm], Laurentii Salvii*. Pp. 1–532 [1766] pp. 533–1327 [1767].
- McIntosh, W.C. 1885. Report on the Annelida Polychaeta collected by H.M.S. Challenger during the years 1873–1876. Report on the Scientific Results of the Voyage of H.M.S. Challenger during the years 1873–76. Zoology. 12 (part 34): i-xxxvi, 1– 554.
- Monniot, F. 1983. Ascidies littorales de Guadeloupe. 1. Didemnidae.– Bulletin du Muséum national d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris series 4 (5): A (1) : 3–49.
- Moore, J.P. 1904. New Polychaeta from California.– Proceedings of the Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia 56: 484–503.
- . 1905. Five new species of *Pseudopotamilla* from the Pacific coast of North America.– Proceedings of the Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia 1: 555–569.
- . 1923. The polychaetous annelids dredged by the U.S.S. "Albatross" off the coast of southern California in 1904. IV. Spionidae to Sabellariidae.– Proceedings of the Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia 75: 179–259.
- Palma-Neri, M.Z.D. & J.R. Bastida-Zavala. 2024(2025). Poliquetos (Annelida: Polychaeta) en estructuras artificiales de tres puertos de Oaxaca, Pacífico sur de México.– Boletín del Instituto Oceanográfico de Venezuela 63 (2): 102–167.
- Pech, D., M.A. Tovar-Hernández, J.R. Bastida-Zavala, L.F. Carrera-Parra, J.A. de León-González, V.H. Delgado-Blas, V. Díaz-Castañeda, C.M. Galván-Villa, M.E. García-Garza, A- Martínez Arce, P. Salazar-Silva & S.I. Salazar-Vallejo. 2023. Protocolo para el muestreo, análisis y estudio la biota portuaria en México. Universidad Autónoma de Nuevo León, Monterrey, México. 38 pp.
- Perkins, T.H. 1984. Revision of *Demonax* Kinberg, *Hypsicomus* Grube, and *Notaulax* Tauber, with a review of *Megalomma* Johansson from Florida (Polychaeta: Sabellidae.– Proceedings of the Biological Society of Washington 97 (2): 285–368.
- Ramos-Morales, A., J.D. Gómez-Vásquez, M.S. García-Madrigal, & J.R. Bastida-Zavala. 2024. Fouling invertebrates from PVC plates at Chahué Marina, Oaxaca, Southern Pacific coast of Mexico.– Check List 20 (3): 728–760.
- Read, G.B., G. Inglis, P. Stratford, S.T. Ahyong, S.T. 2011. Arrival of the alien fanworm *Sabella spallanzanii* (Gmelin, 1791)(Polychaeta: Sabellidae) in two New Zealand harbours.– Aquatic Invasions 6 (3): 273–9.
- Reish, D.J. 1963. A quantitative study of the benthic polychaetous annelids of Bahía de San Quintin, Baja California.– Pacific Naturalist 3: 399–436.
- Rodríguez-Valencia, J.A. 2004. Respuesta de los poliquetos bentónicos a la variabilidad ambiental y condiciones El Niño en Bahía Petacalco (Guerrero, México).– Ciencias Marinas 30 (4): 515–526.
- Rouse, G.W., F. Pleijel, & E. Tilic. 2022. Annelida. Oxford University Press, Glasgow, Great Britain. 418 pp.
- Schmarda, L.K. 1861. Neue Wirbellose Thiere: Beobachtet und Gesammelt auf einer Reise um die Erdr 1853 bis 1857. In Turbellarien, Rotatorien und Anneliden. Leipzig, Verlag von Wilhelm Engelmann. Erster Band, Zweite Hälfte.
- Spalding, M.D., H.E. Fox, G.R. Allen, N. Davidson, Z.A. Ferdaña, M. Finlayson, B.S. Halpern, M.A. Jorge, A. Lombana, S.A. Lourie, et al. 2007. Marine ecoregions of the World: A bioregionalization of coastal and shelf areas.– BioScience 57: 573–583.
- Sun, Y., E. Wong, M.A. Tovar-Hernández, J. Williamson, & E.K. Kupriyanova. 2016. Is *Hydroides brachyacantha* (Serpulidae, Annelida) a wide spread species.– Invertebrate systematics 30 (1): 41–59.
- Tauber, P. 1879. Annulata Danica. En Kritisk Revision af de i Danmark Fundne Annulata Chaetognatha, Gephyrea, Balanoglossi, Discophoreae, Oligochaeta, Gymnocopa og Polychaeta. Reitzel, Kobenhavn, 143 pp.
- Tovar-Hernández, M.A. 2007. Revision of *Chone* Krøyer, 1856 (Polychaeta: Sabellidae) from North America and descriptions of four new species.– Journal of Natural History 41 (9–12): 511–566.
- . 2008. Phylogeny of *Chone* Krøyer, 1856 (Polychaeta: Sabellidae) and related genera.– Journal of Natural History 42(33–34): 2193–2226.
- , & L.F. Carrera-Parra. 2011. *Megalomma* Johansson, 1925 (Polychaeta: Sabellidae) from America and other world-wide localities, and phylogenetic relationships within the genus.– Zootaxa 2861: 1–71.
- , J.A. de León-González, & M.E. Hendrickx. 2025. Polychaeta collected during the research cruises TALUD aboard the R/V "El Puma" in the Mexican Pacific: Sabellidae and Serpulidae.– Zootaxa (under revision).
- , ———, & E.K. Kupriyanova. 2022. New records of invasive tubeworms (*Ficopomatus*, Serpulidae) in Mexico.– Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom, 102 (8): 553–564.
- & H. Dean. 2014. A new gregarious sabellid worm from the Gulf of California reproducing by spontaneous fission (Polychaeta-Sabellidae).– Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom 94 (05): 935–946.

- _____, C.M. Galván-Villa, & J.A. de León-González. 2024. *Pyrgopolon ctenactis* (Annelida: Serpulidae) in Manzanillo, Colima, Mexican Central Pacific.– *GEOMARE ZOOLOGICA* 6(1): 29–35.
- _____, M.E. García-Garza, J.A. de León-González. 2020. Sclerozoan and fouling sabellid worms (Annelida: Sabellidae) from Mexico with the establishment of two new species. *Biodiversity Data Journal* 8: e57471.
- _____, & L.H. Harris. 2010. *Parasabella* Bush, 1905, replacement name for the polychaete genus *Demonax* Kinberg, 1867 (Annelida: Polychaeta: Sabellidae).– *ZooKeys* 60: 13–19.
- _____, & P. Knight-Jones. 2006. Species of *Branchiomma* (Polychaeta: Sabellidae) from the Caribbean Sea and Pacific coast of Panama.– *Zootaxa* 1189: 1–37.
- _____, N. Méndez, & J. Salgado-Barragán. 2009a. *Branchiomma bairdi* (McIntosh, 1885): a Caribbean hermaphrodite fan worm in the south-eastern Gulf of California (Polychaeta: Sabellidae).– *Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom, Marine Biodiversity Records* 2: E43.
- _____, N. Méndez, & T.F. Villalobos-Guerrero. 2009b. Fouling tubicolous polychaetes worms from the south-eastern Gulf of California: Sabellidae and Serpulidae.– *Systematics and Biodiversity* 7: 1–18.
- _____, & A. Pineda-Vera. 2008. Sistemática y estrategias reproductivas del poliqueto sabélido *Bispira brunnea* (Treadwell, 1917) del Caribe mexicano.– *Ciencia y Mar* XI (33): 3–14.
- _____, P. Salazar-Silva & J.A. de León-González. 2019. Lista faunística comentada de gusanos poliquetos en la bahía de La Paz, Baja California Sur, México (Annelida: Polychaeta) y nuevos registros.– *Revista Mexicana de Biodiversidad* 90: e902764.
- _____, & S.I. Salazar-Vallejo. 2006. Sabellids (Polychaeta: Sabellidae) from the Grand Caribbean.– *Zoological Studies* 45 (1): 24–66.
- _____, & _____. 2008. Caruncle in *Megalomma* Johansson, 1925 (Polychaeta: Sabellidae) and the description of a new species from the Eastern Tropical Pacific.– *Journal of Natural History* 42 (29–30): 1951–1973.
- _____, H. ten Hove, O. Vinn, M. Zatoñ, J.A. de León-González, & M.E. García-Garza. 2020. Fan worms (Annelida: Sabellidae) from Indonesia collected by the Snellius II Expedition (1984) with the descriptions of three new species and tube microstructure.– *PeerJ* 8: e9692.
- _____, T.F. Villalobos-Guerrero, E. Kupriyanova, & Y. Sun. 2016. A new fouling *Hydroides* (Annelida, Sabellida, Serpulidae) from southern Gulf of California.– *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom* 96 (3): 693–705.
- _____, _____, B. Yáñez-Rivera, J.M. Aguilar-Camacho, & I.D. Ramírez-Santana. 2012. Guía de invertebrados acuáticos exóticos en Sinaloa. Geomare, A. C., USFWS, INE-SEMARNAT. Mazatlán, México. 41 pp.
- _____, & B. Yáñez-Rivera. 2012a. Ficha técnica y análisis de riesgo de *Branchiomma bairdi* (McIntosh, 1885) (Polychaeta: Sabellidae). Capítulo IX. Pp: 167–190. In: Low Pfeng, A.M. & E.M. Peters Recagno (eds.). *Invertebrados marinos exóticos en el Pacífico mexicano*. Geomare, A. C., INE-SEMARNAT. México. 235 pp.
- _____, & _____, 2012b. Ficha técnica y análisis de riesgo de *Ficopomatus miamiensis* (Treadwell, 1934) (Polychaeta: Serpulidae). Capítulo X. Pp: 193–212. In: Low Pfeng, A.M. & E.M. Peters Recagno (eds.). *Invertebrados marinos exóticos en el Pacífico mexicano*. Geomare, A. C., INE-SEMARNAT. México. 235 pp.
- _____, _____, & J.L. Bortolini-Rosales. 2011. Reproduction of the invasive fan worm *Branchiomma bairdi* (Polychaeta: Sabellidae).– *Marine Biology Research* 7 (7): 710–718.
- _____, _____, T.F. Villalobos-Guerrero, J.M. Aguilar-Camacho, & I.D. Ramírez-Santana. 2014. *Invertebrados marinos exóticos en el Golfo de California*. Capítulo 16. Pp. 381–409. In: Low Pfeng, A., P. Quijón & E. Peters (eds.). *Especies invasoras acuáticas: casos de estudio en ecosistemas de México*. Segunda parte, distribución de especies invasoras: casos de estudio. Secretaría de Medio Ambiente y Recursos Naturales (SEMARNAT), Instituto Nacional de Ecología y Cambio Climático (INECC), University of Prince Edward Island (UPEI).
- Treadwell, A.L. 1906. Polychaetous annelids of the Hawaiian Islands collected by the steamer Albatross in 1902.– *Bulletin of the United States Fish Commission* 23 (3): 1145–1181.
- _____. 1917. Polychaetous annelids from Florida, Porto Rico, Bermuda and the Bahamas.– *Carnegie Institute of Washington Publication* 251: 255–272.
- Villalobos-Guerrero, T.F., & M.A. Tovar-Hernández. 2013. Una especie nueva de *Pseudonereis* (Polychaeta: Nereididae) de Mazatlán (Golfo de California), incluyendo una clave para las especies del mundo.– *Revista Mexicana de Biodiversidad* 84: 774–781.
- _____, & _____. 2014. Poliquetos errantes (Polychaeta: Errantia) esclerobiontes del puerto de Mazatlán (México).– *Boletín de Investigaciones Marinas y Costeras del INVEMAR* 43 (1): 43–87.

Webster, H.E. 1879. The Annelida Chaetopoda of the Virginian coast.– Transactions of the Albany Institute 9: 202–272.

Yáñez-Rivera, B., M.A. Tovar-Hernández, C.M. Galván-Villa, & E. Ríos-Jara. 2020. Tubicolous polychaete worms (Annelida) from Bahía de Chamela Islands Sanctuary, Mexico, with the description of a new bamboo worm.– Biodiversity Data Journal 8: e57572.

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